

THE PEARLS PROGRAM AND THE TECHNOLOGY OF WORKING ON THEM IN READING LITERACY LESSONS

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Abstract: This article presents international assessment studies of students in reading literacy classes in elementary grades and ideas about ensuring student participation in them.

Key words: PISA, OECD organization, PIRLS, international assessment, program, reading literacy, control, test, international association, educational institution.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены международные исследования по оцениванию учащихся на занятиях по читательской грамотности в начальных классах и идеи по обеспечению участия учащихся в них.

Ключевые слова: PISA, организация ОЭСР, PIRLS, международная оценка, программа, грамотность чтения, контроль, тест, международная ассоциация, образовательное учреждение.

The State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan reached an agreement on participation in international assessment studies, including PISA-2021 international assessment studies with the OECD organization.

PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) is an international assessment system that assesses the quality of reading and comprehension levels of primary school students in different countries. This type of test is designed to be conducted once every 5 years, and according to the results of its latest research in 2016, the Russian Federation is leading.

The International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement is an international partnership of national research institutes, research agencies, scholars, and analysts working to evaluate, understand, and improve education worldwide. More than 60 countries and more than 100 educational institutions participate in this network of non-profit and independent organizations. Since 1958, the IEA has distinguished itself from other international organizations by creating measures and acceptable recommendations to eliminate deficiencies in the educational system in the process of assessing students' literacy in mathematics, natural sciences, and reading potential.

At the meeting on January 25, the initiative of Uzbekistan's participation in the research of the PIRLS program for 2021 was welcomed by the IEA organization with great applause, and it was noted that the organization will provide all necessary support and recommendations. In addition, organizational issues related to participation in PIRLS-2021 research, i.e. conditions of participation, stages of research implementation, guidelines for effective organization of research and many other tasks were discussed in detail at the meeting.

As part of the **PIRLS** research, the quality of reading and the level of understanding of the read text of the 4th graders of countries with different educational systems are studied. The choice of 4th grade students for these studies is important because it is precisely in the fourth year of study that students have a high level of learning, form their ability to acquire knowledge in further education, and thus to the present time. helps in successful adaptation. In most countries, children start school at the age of 6. But in England and New Zealand, education starts at the age of 5. Therefore, students from the 5th grade, not the 4th grade, will participate in the project. The age of the students whose reading and text comprehension quality is checked is 10.5 years. Since children in Eastern countries start school at the age of 7, 10.7-10.9-year-old students will participate in the study.

PIRLS research is coordinated by the International Association of Educational Institutions (IEA). The PIRLS project is considered a leader among international studies on determining the level of development of reading ability of primary school students.

PIRLS studies have been conducted at the level of primary education for 5 years since 2001. It has a high place among international studies. The number of countries participating in this program is increasing every year. It has been held 4 times since 2001. The last PIRLS research was conducted in 2016. So far, 35 to 50 countries have participated.

The goals and objectives of the PIRLS International Research, the procedure for conducting it.

PIRLS Educational Testing Service (USA), Statistics Canada (Canada), Data Processing Center of the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (Germany) and Boston College International Center (USA) are participating The participation of these organizations in the development of pedagogical measures for evaluating the educational achievements of schoolchildren based on experimentally tested international standards allows to ensure the high quality of the organization and conduct of PIRLS research.

The purpose of the PIRLS study is to compare reading comprehension levels of fourth-grade students from different countries around the world, as well as to identify differences in reading literacy across national education systems.

According to the international dictionary of research, "reader literacy" is the ability of a person to understand and logically understand the various written languages necessary to fully express himself in life and achieve his goals.

PIRLS research aims to solve the following problems:

- development of objective measures and tools reflecting world priorities in the field of education;
- comparative assessment of the effectiveness of the organization of the country's educational process;
- identification of contextual factors that influenced the research results;
- having evidence-based information recognized by the international community.

The object of research is the educational achievements of primary school graduates, as it collects all the knowledge and skills of teaching in the fourth academic year. At this age, students should be well versed in reading so that they can use a variety of texts in structure and format to continue successfully in mainstream school.

PIRLS will be held according to the plan of the International Center. Countries with large territories are divided into layers corresponding to administrative division. In order to select strata, data on the number of students in the studied population are collected in each

region. It is carried out by a probabilistic method, taking into account the number of students, by selecting schools in all countries.

Selection of research participants is carried out in several stages. At the first stage, the national coordinators of the participating countries send the lists of all schools (city, village, village) in the country to the International Coordination Center. About 150 schools from each country are then selected using a special program using the "random number method".

Schools selected by international experts to participate in the study provide the National Coordinator with lists of students of the fourth grade, fully corresponding to the data in the classes. The list of 4th grade students is entered into the database and sent to the International Coordination Center.

Standardization and research procedure:

Studying PIRLS is carried out in strict accordance with the guidelines and rules developed by a single center for standardization of reading technology in all countries participating in the project.

Every step of the research - sampling, translation and adaptation, testing and interrogation, data verification and processing - is supervised by international experts. For example, translations of test items and respondents' questionnaires were sent to international experts for further verification. In each region, the National Coordinator will coordinate with the Regional Education Directorate with the Regional Coordinating Center responsible for organizing and conducting the research. Accordingly, a school coordinator is appointed in each school selected for the study. The person conducting the test is selected from among experienced professional teachers who do not teach in the tested class and school. During the test, international observers are divided into selected schools. They are appointed by the International Association for Academic Performance Assessment (IAPA) from among independent experts in the field of education of the participating country (they may be representatives of international and non-governmental organizations). The appointed observer in Uzbekistan is required to speak Uzbek, Russian and English.

According to the developed special requirements, the International Observer will personally select a certain number of schools to participate. This ensures the objectivity of the study results.

Reading order:

- Each school, class, parallel, student has its own international identification code (student ID), personal version number, participation status.
- In order to ensure the reliability of the material received 1 hour before the start of the test, the school coordinator opens the closed package of materials and hands it over to the person conducting the test.
- All questions that arose during the test, reasons for avoiding technology and research methods are recorded in a special protocol.
- Upon completion, the researcher should return the student responses and respondent questionnaires to the school coordinator.
- Additional tests are conducted if, for objective reasons, less than 90% of students participated in the main test.

Description of research tools.

International PIRLS research tools include:

- Notebook with texts and questions.

- Student questionnaire.
- Teacher's information.
- Parents form.
- Form of school administration.
- National handbook of observers.
- Regional coordinating manual.
- Handbook for the school coordinator.
- Instructional manual.
- A guide to job evaluation and response coding.

Each participant of the research is given a notebook with texts and assignments.

The first text is fiction or funny stories, pictures or fairy tales, and the second is informative (most often a story about animals). 12-15 questions are attached to each text. Thus, the results of PIRLS research conducted in different countries are widely discussed by the pedagogical community. Mechanisms for monitoring the results of schoolchildren's achievements are being introduced, educational technologies and requirements for the educational achievements of primary schoolchildren are being considered. Research on the literacy of schoolchildren, pedagogical teams and innovative teachers on the basis of international test tasks is aimed not only at evaluating the academic achievements of students, but also primarily at the formation of reading culture and skills, which is an important factor in the education of the country's youth.

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